

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

“MOLLA NASREDDIN” - THE LEADER OF THE LITERARY PERIOD

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Abstract

Jalil Mammadguluzadeh is a great figure who has played an exceptional role in the promotion of Azerbaijani literature to a new stage and has formed an entire literary school. The rich heritage of the writer's artistic achievements, the ideology of Azerbaijanism has come to be widely used as the leading factor in the socio-political thought of the era. The artist has created a colorful gallery of realities that reflect the realities of life, a comprehensive picture of the social environment, and the artistic-aesthetic value carrier. "Molla Nasreddin" is a product of Mirza Jalil, which is widely spread in Azerbaijan and abroad and has a strong impact on the development of ideas of freedom and national revival.

Keywords: "Molla Nasreddin", national press, Jalil Mammadguluzadeh, Azerbaijan realism, historical-social thinking.

INTRODUCTION.

Azerbaijan's ethnocentrism is one of the important directions of the 20th century Azerbaijani literary criticism. From the day of the creation of Molla Nasreddin, the most spectacular publication of the Eastern, Turkish-Islamic press, not only in our national press, but in the focus of literary-historical thought since 1906. There are several reasons for this. It was the great and sacred mission stated in the first issue of the magazine, "I have spoken to you, my Muslim brothers". People were interested in the first day, what Molla Nasreddin meant. It soon became clear that the magazine sent a letter to the "Muslim Brotherhood". And with this statement, he attracted the attention of the literary-historical thought. Molla Nasreddin writer A.Hagverdiyev writes: "The first issue was in the beginning of May. This number exploded as a bomb among the townspeople ... The effect of the magazine on the population of Shusha can not be described as a pen ". The second reason was that, as the great writer Y.V.Chamanzaminli said, "Molla Nasreddin" create "a great literary period ... the head of literary period". It was Molla Nasreddin's literary school, namely the representatives of this school - J.Mammadguluzade, M.A.Sabir, Omar Faig, A.Hagverdiyev, Ali Nazmi, Aligulu Gemkuser and others, founded the basis of critical realism as literary method and literary trend in Azerbaijani literature, And his poetics and aesthetics. Mirza Jalil acknowledges that "Molla Nasreddin - not one single man's work. "Molla Nasreddin is a collection of a few of my dear colleagues, and only I am their elder friend." This confession is not only of historical truth, but also of a great civilian intelligence

The third reason was that Molla Nasreddin was born during the most important period of the history of Azerbaijan - the 1905-1907 revolution of the world, which upset the world. Mirza Jalil correctly guided the course of history and could hear that the national renaissance of the 20th century was in need of such a

magazine. Mirza Jalil himself, before all else, wrote in his entirety: "Molla Nasreddin created nature itself, and created it itself ... His first issue was glorified, not only in the Caucasian Muslims, but also in the Greater East And he was glorified. "

Magazine had to overcome a challenging struggle to become the head of our national press. His pages contained the greatest national and historical truths about Azerbaijan. He stood at the forefront of the struggle for mother tongue, changed into living classical example of writing and speaking in his mother tongue. The Azerbaijani intellectuals have since been highly appreciated highly by the literary-historical significance of this publication. Firudin bey Kocharli, the founder of Azerbaijani literary criticism, wrote: From starting "Molla Nasreddin" magazine has created a lively interest among the Muslims of our country, issue of the magazine ... Well-educated and cultural Azerbaijani Jalil Mammadguluzadeh with the collaboration group of intelligent Muslims ... With the laugh "Molla Nasreddin" castigated the muslim societies defects they published the magazine. " In the twentieth century as genius Alibey Huseynzadeh, Uzeyir Hajibeyli, Ahmed Aghaoglu, Nariman Narimanov, Mahammadaga Shahtakhtli, M.A.Rasulzadeh, F.B.Kocharli were very valuable remarks about "Molla Nasreddin". Research of Molla Nasreddin began to the 30-s of the XX century. These years were generally the era of literary criticism and literary criticism. In those years, Molla Nasreddin magazine had completed its 25-year-long, magnificent and honorable mission. "Molla Nasreddin" was engraved in the memory of the people and public opinion with Jalil Mammadguluzadeh. From the period of Molla Nasreddin, who did not understand the era of the new proletarian dictatorship, was brought to the center of analysis and criticism. The well-known writer and ethnographer, a skilled diplomat Y.V.Chamanzaminli, wrote in his article titled "Literary Period Head" (Literature Newspaper January 30, 1934):

"Which was creator literary period that leads to revolution in our social life, the leadership of the magazine since 25 years This great figure ... today is not among us. But his works live. He convinced belong to a great scribe both the subject and types and anecdotes, belong to a great puzzle. Molla is a great originality. " Mirza Jalil and "Molla Nasreddin" went to Tabriz in 1921, refuse to cooperate corrupt organization of the "Mubariz Alliance of Unity". Azerbaijan Education Commissioner D.Bunyadzade's said his speech at the Azerbaijan (February 1921): "Probably most of you remain. A few years ago, at the time of Nicholas, "Molla Nasreddin" was published. Editor of the magazine is in Iran. We have taken steps to return him to Baku. And soon Mirza Jalil returned to Baku. But after this return, as they say, his day was black. If he had not died in 1933, his blessed name would be in the first place in the list of 1937 repression victims ...

The first great monograph about Mirza Jalil in the 1930s was written by young and prominent critic Ali Nazim. Ali Nazim wrote in his biography in 1933 that he planned a monograph in the amount of 6 copyrighted books called as "Molla Nasreddin as an Artist". It was one of the first Soviet scientists, a candidate dissertation of A.Nazim's. This monograph was published in 1936 with several editions of the editorial office of M.Huseyn. Meanwhile, he had black clouds of 1937 over Nazim's head. Therefore the mass edition of the work is stopped. The only copy of that monograph was the personal archive corresponding member of ANAS, of the late professor Abbas Zamanov. It was called "Jalil Mammadguluzade (Molla Nasreddin)". This unfortunate monograph was the basis of theory of Molla Nasreddin. Because in this work, Mirza Jalil and "Molla Nasreddin" are included in parts of whole unity literary-historical thought as synonymous names, parts of a whole unity. A.Nazim also attracts Molla Nasreddin, Mirza Jalili, as an independent stage of Azerbaijani realism. The author explained this stage of realism by the smile of Molla Nasreddin: "To his laugh peculiarity, it should be sarcasm with the tears. This laughter takes the laughs of those who try to hide their crying ... But this laugh does not always stay that, it turns to hate, is a sharp weapon, destroys a bullet and burn. When Ali Nazim was in prison the second monograph of Mirza Ibrahimov's work "Great Democrat" was published in 1939, which was completed as a scientific system of the theory of Molla Nasreddin. This work was written by the Marxist-Leninist methodology, the ideological doctrine at the style wanted of the Soviet regime. The author strives to present the literary-historical value of Mirza Jalil and Molla Nasreddin in the context of the democratic-public opinion in Azerbaijan, in the context of the issue of M.Ahundzadeh. This monograph, which is valuable for its time, aims to reflect the journal's public-philosophical position in chapters "Molla Nasreddin", "Molla Nasreddin", "Struggle of Two Styles". Contradiction of the Marxist-Leninist methodology, M. Ibrahimov defined the democratization of "Molla Nasreddin" and Mirza Jalil in the book "Molla Nasreddin" and "Fuyuzat" in the chapter "The struggle of two styles". We read the monograph: From the first issue of "Molla Nasreddin", it criticise badness of bourgeois-

feudal life. From the first issue of the magazine, he started writing with his own simple folklore. Jalil Mammadguluzadeh called for democratic methods for promoting democratic ideas ... It was important to understand the language of the people, and to understand that his own life was unbearable.

"Molla Nasreddin" was like a sun that cleanses the dark and perverse life.

... Mollanasreddins did not imagine a national renaissance without the participation of the masses.

... "Molla Nasreddin" is a very important and proud hearted in our history of development, in the public life of our people. "

The problem of "Molla Nasreddin" and supporters of Molla Nasreddin has been the focus of attention in the Azerbaijan literary criticism for the whole XX century Both researchers, researchers, philosophers, and philosophers, both linguists and literary critics, have come to terms with this magnificent monument from different perspectives and approved the importance in our national-historical fate. MSOrdubadi, Aziz Sharif, Mir Jalal, Abbas Zamanov, M.Jafar, M.Arif, Ali Sultanli, Q.Mammadli, Aziz Mirahmedov, K.Talibzade, Kh.Alimirzayev, M.Mammadov, F.Huseynov, Y.Garayev Prominent writers and literary critics said valuable ideas that could be the subject of a special scientific-monographic study about Molla Nasreddin in the 50s and 80s of the 20th century.

Academician M.C.Jafarov wrote: "The fame of the power of pen Sabir, Ali Nazim, Jalil Mammadguluzadeh and had gathered around him since 1906, supporter of the Azerbaijan satirist literature with the has exceeded the borders. In the East many talented followers of the late Molla Nasreddin, intellectuals have grown up love and affection in the East". One of the most important research works in the field of Azerbaijani studies is the monograph of the late professor H.Mammadov from "Ekinchi" to "Molla Nasreddin" (1987). In this work which was learned less of the literary-historical and theoretical-aesthetic idea of Azerbaijan in the last period of the XIX century and the beginning of the twentieth century, two magazines was considered, in Azerbaijani press the way of enlightenment of "Molla Nasreddin" was investigated.

Theoretical and historical monograph of Azerbaijan's science we should be especially emphasized: Yashar Garayev. "Realism: Art and Reality (Steps of Azerbaijani Realism)" (1980), Aziz Mirahmedov. "Azerbaijan Molla Nasreddin" (1980) and Isa Habibbeyli "Jalil Mammadguluzade: atmosphere and contemporaries" (1997). The works of Y.Garayev and A.Mirahmedov and the monograph of I.Habibbeyli are generally valuable studies a well-deserved summarizing the theory of 20th centuries theory evolution.

The crucial role of Mirza Jalil and literary school Molla Nasreddin as a critical realism in the monograph "The Stages of Azerbaijani Realism" by Y.Garayev is justified from a theoretical-philosophical point of view. He writes: "Mirza Jalil is the head and great representative of the new realism in the 20th century Azerbaijani artistic thought. In generally from Mirza Jalil, Azerbaijani realism does not recognize the high peaks the road from Zakir to Sabira: the critical realism with Mirza

Jalil upgrade to the highest level. He was not merely a follower of realism of M.F.Ahundzadeh, it was the "banner" of a new stage in the development of realism. After Mirza Fatal, major reforms in Azerbaijani prose, dramatization, literary and social thought take place in the work of Mirza Jalil. "

The monograph of A.Mirahmadov in the monograph "Azerbaijan Molla Nasreddin" is investigated and substantiated by valuable facts fight for the democratization and development outlook of J.Mammadguluzadeh's arrival to the eternal environment and the press. In the fourth chapter of the monograph, especially the founder and editor of "Molla Nasreddin," J.Mammadguluzadeh and the problem of monolithicism are the subject of special investigation along with the sacrifices of the magazine.

CONCLUSION.

Academician I.Habibbeyli's fundamental monograph is completely original research, based on new materials and archive documents. Here, it was searching Mirza Jalil's atmosphere, all stages of his literary, journalistic and social activities, his honorable and painful fate, from the childhood to the last period of his life. The history and solution problems of learners of Molla Nasreddin and Fuyuzat are one of the valuable features of this work. The author provides extensive information about the contemporary of the writer, along with the years of study. The final chapter of the work is devoted to the generation of Mirza Jalil from generation to generation in this huge research work consist of the discovered materials with the supplements it also bringing science into the work as well as practice. Most importantly, I.Habibbeyli does not noticed that the residence period of the "Molla Nasreddin" and "Mirza Jalil" as the history of facts and documents. Here the environment is also studied as a philosophical-aesthetic problem, which is one of the valuable scientific and theoretical qualities of monographs.

The theory of Molla Nasreddin are a whole scientific system with serious theoretical and methodological problems. For a hundred years, the name "Molla Nasreddin" became eternal at the thought of Azerbaijan

historical social and science has formed as a science of Molla Nasreddin theory. Investigating monographs in the context of this scientific Azerbaijani literary criticism has become an urgent historical necessity today.

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